

EXPLORING ACCEPTANCE FACTORS OF INTERNET OF THINGS IN SMART HOME

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ABSTRACT

With Internet of Things multiple advantages like healthcare, energy control, transportation, and the establishment of smart environments such as smart homes, it has become a focal point for researchers. However, human tendencies to initially resist and adapt to novel technologies necessitate a thorough exploration of factors influencing the acceptance and utilization of both information technology and the Internet of Things. Smart homes, as a cutting-edge IoT application, hold particular significance. This study considered the acceptance factors of IoT within smart homes, seeking to establish a model that enhances user acceptance. The research targeted students using the Internet of Things, and 384 people were studied by random sampling. To study, a questionnaire based on UTAUT2 model was designed. The study conducted a comprehensive analysis using the SPSS software and the linear regression test. Key findings indicate that performance expectancy, trust, and hedonic motivation positively influence attitudes towards the Internet of Things. Furthermore, facilitating conditions and attitude towards IoT demonstrate a positive impact on behavioral intention. This study contributes valuable insights for fostering a comprehensive understanding of IoT acceptance dynamics, particularly in the context of smart homes, and lays the groundwork for a model aimed at augmenting user acceptance.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of interconnected objects that share data to perform a task and provide services in different applications. Its main purpose is to improve our daily life and change the way we do different things. IoT applications cover a wide range from home to industry (Tewari & Gupta, 2020).

IoT is an innovative framework facilitating the extension of the Internet to encompass physical objects and things. This interconnected paradigm establishes a dynamic global network comprising billions of diverse intelligent objects. These things exhibit the capability to sense, gather, share, and exchange information through communication and mutual interaction.

The spectrum of smart things within the IoT ecosystem spans a range of devices, such as computers, mobile phones, heart rate monitors, smart lighting, electricity meters, smart locks, motion detection sensors, and temperature sensors.

Projections indicate that by the year 2025, the global IoT market is anticipated between \$3.9 trillion and \$11.1 trillion (Shuhaiber & Mashal, 2019). The significant impact of the IoT extends to reshaping the way of working, connection, communication, and products and services. Nowadays, the prevalence of IoT has experienced remarkable growth, equivalent to approximately 26 smart things per person (Chatfield & Reddick, 2019).

Specifically, the Internet of Things establishes the infrastructure necessary for measuring, identifying, tracking, and monitoring the connectivity of things. This capability aims to simplify people's lives by automating tasks (Metallo et al., 2018). As a result, IoT has far-reaching implications across numerous sectors, including humanity, energy-saving, communication, business, health, education, science, security, government, automation, and entertainment (Zeinab & Elmustafa, 2017).

The Internet of Things, like any emerging technology, comes with challenges along with its benefits and applications. Within the realm of the IoT, challenges emerge in the areas of data ownership and control, data sharing, as well as concerns related to privacy and security (Gubbi et al., 2013). Furthermore, price, scalability, data volumes, software complexity, fault tolerance, wireless communications, and power supply are some of the challenges of implementing and using the IoT (Zeinab & Elmustafa, 2017).

In the contemporary landscape, the Internet of Things has facilitated the connectivity of a many devices to the network, with the smart home emerging as a main service within this ecosystem. Globally renowned companies are leading the launch of smart home services and products, leveraging the power of the IoT.

A smart home is characterized as an intelligent environment capable of acquiring and utilizing knowledge about its residents and their surroundings, ultimately adapting to achieve comfort and efficiency objectives. These services encompass the control and automation of lighting, heating, ventilation, air conditioning, and security. Furthermore, they extend to household appliances such as washers, dryers, gas stoves, refrigerators, and freezers (Shin et al., 2018).

Nevertheless, the pace of smart home expansion has fallen short of expectations, attributed to two key factors: technical limitations and the acceptance of smart home. Traditionally,

research in the smart home domain has predominantly emphasized the technical complexities and the necessary infrastructure for its establishment but the crucial technologies for smart home implementation did not prepare. This emphasis on the technical aspects has, regrettably, resulted in a neglect of the user's acceptance, behavior, and utilization. Consequently, despite the rapid proliferation of smart homes, a significant gap persists, demanding further research into user acceptance and the commercialization aspects of these homes (Yang et al., 2017).

On the flip side, a home is characterized as a calm environment, both emotionally and physically, where individuals can effectively carry out their responsibilities (Kraybill, 2005). One of the concerns of researchers in the field of smart home technologies is that they do not disturb the peace of people at home. Consequently, the growth rate of this technology has been relatively subdued in recent years. Despite the ongoing emergence of Internet of Things benefits, promising to enhance people's lives, foster independence, and deliver superior services, this technology remains entangled in challenges, including privacy risks, issues of trust, and data security concerns (Marikyan et al., 2021).

Considering the existing gap in the development of smart homes, our research has strategically concentrated on the specific facet of Internet of Things acceptance within smart home environments. Our objective is to explore the nuanced factors influencing users' decisions to adopt IoT technologies in smart homes. To accomplish this, we have employed the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2) model as our theoretical framework. UTAUT2 is recognized for its efficacy in comprehensively capturing the dynamics of technology adoption, making it a fitting choice for our investigation into the adoption patterns and determinants within the area of smart home technologies.

The remainder of the article follows this organizational structure. In Section 2, we describe the background. Section 3 provides a detailed overview of the methodology employed in this study, encompassing a comprehensive explanation of the research model. Section 4 is dedicated to presenting results and engaging in a large discussion. Subsequently, Section 5 addresses future work. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusion.

RELATED WORK

In 2018, Lee and colleagues tried to investigate the effect of perceived privacy of Internet of Things on the consumers' willingness to use it. They divided the perceived privacy benefit into two dimensions and perceived privacy risk into three dimensions, direct benefit of customized service and indirect benefit of efficiency innovation of suppliers, passive user data collection, predictive use of personal data, and market discrimination, respectively. Their results showed that consumers who received more benefits from customized services were more likely to use smart home appliances, and consumers who received more benefits from efficient supplier innovation were more likely to use remote home services. On the other hand, predictive use of personal data had a positive effect on the willingness of consumers of Internet of Things technology (Lee et al., 2018).

In 2019, Chouk and Mani looked for what factors reduce resistance to smart services and what factors increase the resistance, specially in the banking sector. Finally, they concluded that consumer lifestyle factors decrease their resistance, and on the contrary, innovation-related factors (such as perceived security, perceived complexity) and ecosystem-related factors increase the resistance to smart services (Chouk & Mani, 2019).

Boer et al. examined the skills needed to use the Internet of Things. In addition, they studied the relationship between these skills and adopting and using of the Internet of Things. The results show that IoT skills directly and positively affect the use of Internet of Things and the attitude towards Internet of Things has no effect on acceptance. This may be due to the lack of knowledge of users about the impact of using the IoT on their privacy and quality of life (de Boer et al., 2019). However, Shuhaiber and Mashal have investigated the factors influencing user acceptance using the extended TAM model due to the slow speed of acceptance of smart homes. In this model, the factors of trust, awareness, enjoyment, and perceived risks have been added to the TAM model to investigate the intention of users to use smart homes. The results showed that trust, awareness, enjoyment, perceived risks, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use have a significant impact on the attitude towards smart homes, which subsequently have a positive effect on the intention to use smart homes (Shuhaiber & Mashal, 2019).

In 2017, Park et al investigated the factors affecting the adoption of Internet of Things in smart homes. They used TAM technology acceptance model and five variables in this research: perceived enjoyment, perceived connectedness, compatibility, perceived control, perceived cost. Their results showed that compatibility, connectedness, and control have a positive effect on users' technology acceptance behavior and cost has a negative effect on users' technology acceptance behavior (Park et al., 2017). Therefore, there were many contradictions between surveys and some of them used few variables in acceptance of internet of things in smart homes, in this study we considered more factors in a new population.

METHODOLOGY

Considering that recent studies show that young people are more willing to use new technologies such as the Internet of Things and the smart home (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020), we selected university students for this study. In this article, the statistical population studied are male and female students aged 18-50. To determine the sample size, we used Cochran formula, which shows the required sample size of 384 people for this research. Furthermore, we used random sampling to collect samples.

Given that Tehran serves as the capital of Iran and boasts a higher level of technological advancement compared to other cities, we conducted our sampling in Tehran to ensure access to the latest technologies. Subsequently, we utilized a random selection process, choosing various universities, and then randomly distributed questionnaires to the students for completion.

In this study, we used the sum of several questionnaires to prepare a comprehensive and practical questionnaire. One of

them is a questionnaire based on the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) and includes the factors of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions (Williams et al., 2015). Another questionnaire that we used is the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology 2 (UTAUT2), which is an evolution of the questionnaire of the UTAUT, to which the factors of price value, hedonic motivation, and habit have been added (Tamilmani et al., 2021). Given the emerging and expanding nature of IoT technology, its usage is not yet widespread, resulting in a limited number of individuals use its applications. Consequently, we opted to exclude habit from our measurement model. In addition, we added the factors of security, privacy, and trust in technology to the previous factors of the questionnaire as necessary backgrounds for adaptation (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020). Therefore, we prepared questionnaire with 11 sections (see Figure 1). Answers are based on the Likert scale: strongly agree, agree, moderate, disagree and strongly disagree.

Figure 1: Research Model

After preparing the questionnaire and collecting the data, we entered the data into SPSS software. We also used RapidMiner software to analyze the data and took help from linear regression tests to check the relationship between variables.

Variables Description

In this part, we define the variables comprising the research model. Performance expectancy is the extent to which an individual believes that the utilization of technology will contribute to the attainment of performance objectives within their job. It reflects the perceived value and usefulness of technology. Effort expectancy signifies the perceived ease of using the system and quantifies the level of effort required to fulfill user needs. The more a system simplifies users' lives, the more likely they are to accept and use it. (Fedorko et al., 2021; Sair & Danish, 2018). Social influence comprises the effect of others' opinions and beliefs on the user's attitude and behavioral intentions towards a specific information system. It measures the degree to which key individuals in a person's life endorse the adoption of a new system by that individual (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020; Fedorko et al., 2021). The enjoyable sensation and satisfaction experienced by a user when using a particular technology are referred to as hedonic motivation (Salimon et al., 2017; Tamilmani et al., 2019).

Security risk indicates the level of risk associated with the use of a technology, potentially leading to a lack of security for its users (Paquette et al., 2010). Privacy risk pertains to the potential compromise of a user's privacy when utilizing a technology. Users must comprehend the apprehension associated with the unauthorized use and potential misuse of their personal data (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020).

The concept of trust encompasses an individual's readiness to embrace vulnerability or conduct within a context marked by risk. This definition integrates both emotional and cognitive aspects of trust (Aboobucker & Bao, 2018; Kesharwani & Singh Bisht, 2012).

Facilitating conditions, particularly in the consumer context, denote the resources available to users for employing an information system (Lu et al., 2005).

In the consumer area, price value comprises the thoughtful balance consumers strike between the perceived benefits of an information system and the associated monetary costs. The affordability of any new technology stands out as a pivotal factor to its overall success (Pal et al., 2018).

RESULTS

After obtaining the data, we examined them and there were no invalid or missing data. Before IoT questions, participant answered some questions about their demographic characteristics like age, gender, level of academic knowledge. These demographic data show that the average age of participants were 22.04 ± 5.53 . The highest age was 48 years and the lowest age was 18 years among the participants. As shown in Table I, 83.9 percent of the students participating in this study were undergraduate students, while 13 and 3.1 percent were postgraduate and doctoral students, respectively (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

The field of study of the students was not the same and many engineering and non-engineering fields participated. According to the obtained results, the performance expectancy, social influence, hedonic motivation, and trust had a positive effect on the attitude toward Internet of Things; while there was no significant effect of effort expectancy, social influence, security risk, and privacy risk on the attitude toward Internet of Things (Table 1).

Table 1: Association of Independent Variables and Attitude Towards IoT (Significance level ($p < 0.05$))

Variables	Coefficients	95% confidential Interval	t	P-value
Performance Expectancy	0.366	0.245-0.486	5.972	0.000*
Effort Expectancy	0.065	-0.054-0.183	1.073	0.284
Social Influence	0.095	-0.024-0.214	1.564	0.119
Hedonic Motivation	0.158	0.063-0.253	3.278	0.001*
Security Risk	-0.016	-0.125-0.093	-0.290	0.772
Privacy Risk	-0.054	-0.134-0.025	-1.350	0.178
Trust	0.135	0.031-0.239	2.555	0.011*

Although we expected that security risk and privacy risk would have a negative effect on the acceptance of Internet of Things by the participants, and this negative effect was also seen in our results, but unfortunately it was not significant. Performance expectancy was the strongest determinant of the attitude towards the Internet of Things, and after that, the hedonic motivation had the key role on the attitude towards the Internet of Things. The variables of facilitating conditions and attitude towards the Internet of Things have a direct positive effect on the behavioral intention to use the Internet of Things (Table 2). Attitude towards the Internet of Things was more influential than the others on the behavioral intention to use the Internet of Things.

Table 2: Regression Results of Behavior Intention (Significance level ($p < 0.05$))

Variables	Coefficients	95% confidential Interval	t	P-value
Facilitating Conditions	0.281	0.182-0.381	5.546	0.000*
Price Value	0.076	-0.012-0.164	1.690	0.092
Attitude towards IoT	0.423	0.337-0.509	9.674	0.000*

DISCUSSION

In this research, which examined the acceptance factors of Internet of Things in smart homes, the results indicated that the performance expectancy, hedonic motivation and trust had a potential effect on people's attitude towards the Internet of Things. Based on the findings of this study, facilitating conditions and attitude towards the Internet of Things are two key factors affecting the behavioral intention towards the Internet of Things in smart homes.

Performance Expectancy

When users perceive that a technology enhances and streamlines their work and daily life, creating tangible benefits, the performance expectancy parameter is positively evaluated. According to the statistical analytics, the

significance level is zero, so the performance expectancy has a positive and significant effect on the attitude towards Internet of Things and smart home technologies. In addition, Aldossari and Sidorova and Kargar Sharif Abad et al. stated that the performance expectancy has a significant and direct positive effect on the attitude towards Internet of Things technologies. The results of these two studies are consistent with our results (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020; Kargar Sharif Abad et al., 2018).

Effort Expectancy

Here, we examined how much the amount of effort a user makes to use a new technology affects his attitude towards Internet of Things. The results obtained for the effort expectancy show there is no correlation between effort expectancy and attitude towards Internet of Things technologies including smart homes in the studied statistical population, but Aldossari and Sidorova have proven that the effort expectancy parameter has a significant and direct positive effect on the attitude towards IoT technologies (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020).

Social Influence

The social influence shows the amount of impact that the community has on the use of the Internet of Things technology by the user. The results of the analysis show that the significance level for the factor is 0.11, which means that social influence has no effect on attitude. Saidi et al.'s report, under the title of evaluation of effective factors in the adoption of Internet of Things technology in building smartness, stated that social influence has a positive effect on the acceptance of Internet of Things technologies in building smartness (Saidi et al., 2017). Pal et al., in their article that investigated the use of Internet of Things in smart homes for the purpose of health care for the elderly, stated that elderly users do not care about the opinions of others and social status. As a result, there was no correlation between social influence and the adoption of Internet of Things. The results of Pal's study were in line with our study, and it is possible that the reason for its ineffectiveness is the lack of importance of students to society's opinions (Pal et al., 2018).

Hedonic Motivation

User satisfaction after using a new technology can be a factor influencing user acceptance. Here, the effect of hedonic motivation on the attitude towards Internet of Things and smart home technologies is significant ($P < 0.01$). Shuhaiber and Mashal and Saidi et al. have proven that the perceived enjoyment has a positive effect on the attitude towards the use of smart homes (Shuhaiber & Mashal, 2019; Saidi et al., 2017).

Privacy Risk

Privacy risk is one of the most important concerns and parameters in using the Internet, Internet of Things, and

smart homes. Based on the results, this factor does not have a significant effect on the attitude towards Internet of Things technologies but Aldossari and Sidorova and Lee et al. showed that privacy risk has a positive effect on attitude (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020; Lee et al., 2018). Our results on privacy risk are inconsistent with these researches, and this may be because users of this technology are not aware of the importance of privacy risk to their information.

Security Risk

The security risk for users can become a concern that affects the adoption and use of new technologies. The results observed in the current research show that, the significance level of the security risk parameter is greater than 0.05 ($P > 0.05$), which means that the security risk does not affect the attitude in the studied society. As Chouk and Mani have said in their research that the perceived security risk creates a significant and positive effect on consumer resistance to smart services (Chouk & Mani, 2019). Conversely, Shuhaiber and Mashal proved that perceived risk has a negative effect on trust in smart homes, and trust has a positive effect on the attitude towards smart homes (Shuhaiber & Mashal, 2019). Thus, the result of this research is inconsistent with the results of the other researches, but considering that the correlation coefficient is negative, it is possible to prove the hypothesis by collecting more diverse data.

Trust

Trust can be considered an important factor in the adoption of new technologies and shows the level of users' belief in new technology such as the Internet of Things. In the obtained results, the level of significance is less than 0.05, and trust has a significant effect on attitude, and these two are dependent of each other. In addition, in another study conducted by Saidi et al., the effect of trust on perceived usefulness and acceptance of Internet of Things technologies in smart building has been investigated, and the results show the positive effect of trust on both parameters (Saidi et al., 2017). On the other hand, the article by Kargar Sharif Abad et al. states that there is no meaningful relationship between trust and the motivation to accept Internet of Things technology (Kargar Sharif Abad et al., 2018).

Facilitating Conditions

Using a new technology for users is always associated with facing unknowns and lack of trust, but if users have the necessary and helpful resources to use the new technology, such as educational resources, then it can affect its acceptance. As expected, the facilitating conditions shows a significant and direct effect on the behavioral intention towards the Internet of Things. However, Aldossari and Sidorova acknowledged that there is no significance level for the effect of the facilitating conditions on behavioral intention towards the Internet of Things (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020). As a result, our study is not the same as the research of Aldossari and Sidorova in this field.

Price Value

Price Value, a measure of whether or not the technology is worth paying for. In the obtained results, the price value has not any significant effect on the behavioral intention towards internet of things. On the contrary, Aldossari and Sidorova have reached in their results that the price value has a positive effect on the behavioral intention towards smart homes (Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020). On the other hand, Park et al. stated that the perceived cost of Internet of Things technologies has a negative and significant effect on the intention to use these technologies (Park et al., 2017).

Attitude Toward Internet of Things

Attitude is an important influencing factor on behavioral intention and it can be considered the main factor for expressing and predicting behavioral intention. In addition, attitude can be a mediator between other factors and behavioral intention. In the results of the research, the factor has a positive effect on the behavioral intention to use Internet of Things technologies. Shuhaiber and Mashal, Aldossari and Sidorova, Park et al., and Khorasani presented that attitude has a positive effect on behavioral intention but in another research by Boer et al. rejected the hypothesis of the effect of attitude towards the Internet of Things on its use. They believe that the users of the Internet of Things are still not fully aware of it and its impact on life (Shuhaiber & Mashal, 2019; Aldossari & Sidorova, 2020; Park et al., 2017; Khorasani, 2016; de Boer et al., 2019).

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

One of the most basic limitations that can greatly affect the results of the research is the lack of knowledge or lack of correct knowledge of the Internet of Things, its use and technologies related to the Internet of Things, especially smart homes. Although the respondents were users of the Internet of Things, they did not have a correct definition of it and smart homes. Possibly attributed to the users' lack of real-life exposure to living in smart homes. For this reason, one of the parameters of the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology model, namely the habit parameter, was removed. But due to the ever-increasing expansion of the Internet of Things and smart homes, this factor can also be measured in future researches. Among other limitations, we can mention the lack of investigation of other influential factors due to the complexities of the research model and data analysis. Future researches might use updated models to find out all dimensions of related factors. Furthermore, for this research, participants were randomly selected from students across various universities in Tehran. Subsequent studies may broaden the scope by including samples from additional universities and cities for a more comprehensive analysis.

CONCLUSION

The relentless advancement of technology, coupled with society's widespread embrace of intelligent devices, has propelled the surge of the Internet of Things (IoT). This

article delves into the investigation of IoT acceptance factors among students in smart homes, aiming to identify and address challenges within this burgeoning system. Utilizing a UTAUT2 model, the study revealed that performance expectancy, trust and hedonic motivation exerted a positive impact on individuals' attitudes towards the Internet of Things. Surprisingly, security risk, privacy risk, and social influence did not exhibit any discernible effect on attitude, defying initial expectations. Intriguingly, the study indicated that attitude towards the Internet of Things, along with considerations such as facilitating conditions, significantly influenced people's behavioral intentions regarding IoT adoption. In essence, these findings underscore the dynamic interplay of factors shaping the embrace of IoT, emphasizing the pivotal role of performance expectations, trust and hedonic motivations in driving positive attitudes and behavioral intentions toward this transformative technology.

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